

the depression of a spot plate. One drop of $1 \times 10^{-7} M$ osmium(VIII) solution is then added to the above mixture. Under these conditions, the colour of the solution does not disappear even in 15 min, whereas, in the absence of iodide, the colour of the solution disappears almost instantaneously.

The identification and dilution limits for the three tests are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—IDENTIFICATION AND DILUTION LIMITS		
Dye(s)	Identification Limit, $\mu\text{g}/0.5 \text{ ml}$	Dilution Limit
<i>Detection of osmium(VIII)</i>		
Neutral Violet and Neutral Red Azocarmine G, Azocarmine B and Wool Fast Blue GL	9×10^{-4}	$1 : 5.5 \times 10^4$
Nigrosine	0.03	$1 : 5.5 \times 10^6$
<i>Detection of arsenic(III)</i>		
Neutral Violet, Neutral Red, Azocarmine G, Azocarmine B, Wool Fast Blue GL and Nigrosine	0.80	$1 : 1.6 \times 10^6$
<i>Detection of iodide</i>		
Neutral Violet and Neutral Red ^a	0.01	$1 : 5.0 \times 10^7$

^a The other four dyes are not suitable in this test.

Interferences : The tests are not vitiated by the presence of the following ions.

Detection of osmium(VIII) : $\text{Ru}^{3+} : 0.05 \mu\text{g}$; $\text{Pt}^{2+} : 0.9 \mu\text{g}$; $\text{Pd}^{2+} : 0.5 \mu\text{g}$; $\text{Au}^{3+} : 0.9 \mu\text{g}$.

Detection of arsenic(III) : $\text{Sb}^{5+} : 0.05 \text{ mg}$; $\text{Sn}^{4+} : 0.05 \text{ mg}$; $\text{Cd}^{2+} : 0.05 \text{ mg}$; $\text{Pb}^{2+} : 0.10 \text{ mg}$.

Detection of iodide : $\text{F}^- : 0.01 \text{ mg}$; $\text{Cl}^- : 0.17 \text{ mg}$; $\text{Br}^- : 0.4 \text{ mg}$; $\text{SCN}^- : 0.03 \text{ mg}$.

Results and Discussion

In our studies on the use of these azine dyes as indicators in the bromatometric titration of arsenic(III) at low concentrations of sulphuric acid and using osmium(VIII) as catalyst⁹, we have observed that the osmium(VIII)-catalysed arsenic(III)-bromate reaction accelerates the slow reaction between the dye and bromate. Based on this observation, we have developed a method for the kinetic-catalytic determination of osmium(VIII)¹⁰. The spot test detections of osmium(VIII) and arsenic(III) are governed by the above-mentioned principle. In our method for the kinetic-catalytic determination of osmium(VIII), we have found that the decolouration of the dyes, Neutral Violet and Neutral Red,

is inhibited in the presence of iodide, and this is the principle underlying the detection of iodide, now reported.

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Studies on the Dielectric Constants of O/W Emulsions Stabilized by Surfactants

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A survey of literature reveals that a number of studies have been carried out experimentally and theoretically on the dielectric properties of colloidally or coarsely dispersed systems¹⁻³. The influence of frequency range⁴, agitation⁵, shear⁶ and temperature⁷ effect has also been studied.

But no attempts have yet been made to study the dielectric constants of kerosene/water and emulsions stabilized with anionic, cationic and non-ionic surfactants under the influence of emulsifier concentration, phase volume ratio, emulsification time and temperature. So the communication will provide the systematic data of dielectric constants of kerosene/water emulsions under the influence of above variables.

Experimental

Materials : Double distilled kerosene oil having sp. gr. 0.7948 g/ml was stored for use in all the experiments. Double distilled water (conductance, $1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was employed throughout the course of the investigation. Sodium dioctyl sulpho succinate (Manoxol IB-anionic surfactant), cetyl pyridinium chloride (CPC-cationic surfactant) and

alkyl aryl polyether (Triton×100 non-ionic surfactant) were B.D.H., London products, and used without further purification.

Preparation of emulsions :

Emulsions were prepared by agent-in-water method⁸ and dielectric constants were measured by conductance capacitance bridge⁹ under the following conditions :

I. Different phase volume ratios viz., 1 : 9, 2 : 8, 3 : 7, 4 : 6 and 5 : 5 were adjusted while the concentration of surfactants was adjusted and the concentration of surfactants was fixed 0.05%.

II. Different emulsifier concentrations viz., 0.01, 0.02, 0.04, 0.08 and 0.10% were varied by keeping phase volume ratio (5 : 5) constant.

III. The temperature effect in the range of 20° to 50 has also been measured.

IV. Both, surfactant concentration (0.05%) and phase volume ratio 1 : 1 were constant while emulsification time viz., 1, 2, 4, 8, 16 min and emulsification temperature viz., 20°, 30°, 40°, 50°, 60° were varied respectively.

The above results are summarised in Tables 1-3.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF PHASE VOLUME RATIO ON THE DIELECTRIC CONSTANTS OF KEROSENE/WATER EMULSIONS

Sl. No.	O/W ratio	Dielectric constants		Triton × 100
		Temp. 30 ± 1°		
		Manoxol IB	OPC	
1.	1 : 9	61.35	62.37	64.50
2.	2 : 8	52.40	53.85	55.85
3.	3 : 7	43.93	45.65	47.12
4.	4 : 6	36.16	37.75	39.65
5.	5 : 5	28.60	29.90	31.04

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF EMULSIFIER CONCENTRATION ON THE DIELECTRIC CONSTANTS OF KEROSENE/WATER EMULSIONS

Sl. No.	O/W ratio 1 : 1	Emulsifier concn. %	Dielectric constants		Triton × 100
			Temp. 30 ± 1°		
			Manoxol IB	OPC	
1.		0.01	31.05	32.70	34.12
2.		0.02	32.35	33.06	36.05
3.		0.04	34.56	35.75	38.06
4.		0.08	36.42	36.41	39.56
5.		0.10	37.15	37.36	40.70

Results and Discussion

The study on the dielectric constants of O/W emulsions of kerosene oil reveals that as the phase volume ratio increases, the dielectric constants decreases as shown in Table 1. Present findings are

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE DIELECTRIC CONSTANTS OF KEROSENE/WATER EMULSIONS

Sl. No.	Temperature °C	Dielectric constants		Triton × 100
		Surfactant concn. 0.05%		
		Manoxol IB	OPC	
1.	20	31.95	32.30	35.15
2.	25	33.84	33.56	37.06
3.	30	35.80	35.90	39.04
4.	35	37.70	37.15	41.71
5.	40	39.56	39.02	43.42
6.	50	40.02	41.25	45.15

in good agreement with previous findings of Hanai *et al*⁶ ; with nujol – CCl₄/water emulsions stabilized by Tween-20 and Span-20. The Table 2 shows that as the concentration of surfactants increases, the dielectric constants of kerosene oil/water emulsions increases.

Table 3 represents the effect of temperature on the dielectric constants of O/W emulsions of kerosene oil. It is clear from the table that as the temperature increases the dielectric constants also increases. This also proves the work of Koizumi *et al*⁷.

The effect of emulsification time and emulsification temperature on the dielectric constants of kerosene oil/water emulsions shows a very slow increase in the values of dielectric constants, with increasing emulsification time and emulsification temperature respectively, which may be due to agglomeration effect. These findings are in good agreement with the findings of previous workers¹⁰.

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